

Analytical magnetic fields of cylindrical & cuboidal magnets

D. CÉBRON†

Université Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, ISTERre, Grenoble, France.

(Received 7 October 2020; revised 25 February 2021; accepted 26 February 2021)

Considering various references of the literature, and using symbolic calculations to correct certain formula, expressions are proposed here to calculate analytically the magnetic field of finite solenoids (which also corresponds to the field of cylindrical magnets) and of cuboidal magnets.

1. Magnetic field generated by a finite solenoid or a finite cylindrical magnet

The magnetic field generated by a cylindrical magnet is the same as the one generated by a finite solenoid, and can be found by converting the formulas (3) and (4) of [Derby & Olbert \(2010\)](#) into elliptic integrals. In cylindrical coordinates (ρ, θ, z) , we consider a solenoid/magnet of radius $\rho = a$ and length L centered on the origin (i.e. $z \in [-L/2; L/2]$). Then, the problem is axisymmetric and we can thus choose any azimuth θ for our calculations. The radial magnetic field is naturally $B_\rho = 0$ for $\rho = 0$, and given elsewhere by

$$B_\rho = \frac{B_r}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{a}{\rho}} \left[\frac{\omega_\pm^2 - 2}{2\omega_\pm} \mathcal{K}(\omega_\pm) + \frac{\mathcal{E}(\omega_\pm)}{\omega_\pm} \right]_{-}^{+}, \quad (1.1)$$

which is actually equation (9) of [Callaghan & Maslen \(1960\)](#) with an opposite sign. In equation (1.1), \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{E} are the complete elliptic integral of the first and second kind, respectively, and we have used

$$\omega_\pm = \sqrt{\frac{4a\rho}{(a+\rho)^2 + \xi_\pm^2}}, \quad (1.2)$$

where $\xi_\pm = z \pm L/2$.

For the axial magnetic field, we define $\gamma = (a - \rho)/(a + \rho)$,

$$\zeta_\pm = \sqrt{\frac{(a - \rho)^2 + \xi_\pm^2}{(a + \rho)^2 + \xi_\pm^2}}, \quad (1.3)$$

and

$$\chi_\pm = \frac{\xi_\pm}{\sqrt{(a + \rho)^2 + \xi_\pm^2}}. \quad (1.4)$$

When $\zeta_+ < 1$, the axial magnetic field is given by

$$B_z = \frac{B_r}{\pi} \frac{a}{a + \rho} \frac{1}{\gamma + 1} \left[\chi_\pm \left(\mathcal{K} \left(\sqrt{1 - \zeta_\pm^2} \right) + \gamma \Pi \left(1 - \gamma^2, \sqrt{1 - \zeta_\pm^2} \right) \right) \right]_{-}^{+}, \quad (1.5)$$

† Email adress for correspondance: david.cebron@univ-grenoble-alpes.fr

FIGURE 1. Magnitude and lines of the magnetic field generated by (a) a cylindrical magnet (b) two attractive aligned cylindrical magnets. Here, we have used the magnet radius a and the residual flux B_r as the respective units of length and magnetic field, choosing $L = 1$, and an inter-magnet distance $W = 2$.

where Π is the complete elliptic integral of the third kind, and if $\zeta_+ \geq 1$, the axial magnetic field is given by

$$B_z = \frac{B_r}{\pi} \frac{a}{a + \rho} \frac{1}{\gamma(\gamma + 1)} \left[\frac{\chi_{\pm}}{\zeta_{\pm}} \left(\gamma \mathcal{K} \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{\zeta_{\pm}^2}} \right) + \Pi \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma^2}, \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{\zeta_{\pm}^2}} \right) \right) \right]_{-}^{+}. \quad (1.6)$$

Then, the mean magnetic field is given by the surface average of the magnetic field \mathbf{B} in a plane (ρ, θ, z) . The mean tilt of \mathbf{B} with respect to the ρ direction is thus given by $\sin \theta = \overline{B_z} / \overline{B}$.

Note finally that the forces between cylindrical magnets cannot be deduced directly from these formulas. To estimate these forces, one can use the formulas given by [Vokoun et al. \(2009\)](#).

2. Magnetic field generated by a finite cuboidal magnet

In this section, we consider a cuboidal magnet (i.e. a rectangular parallelepiped) of size $L_x = 2a$, $L_y = 2b$, $L_z = 2c$ in the x , y , and z direction, respectively. Noting the residual field $\mathbf{B}_r = \mu_0 \mathbf{M}$, with M the (volume) magnetization of the magnet, the magnetic field is given explicitly by [Yang et al. \(1990\)](#) for \mathbf{M} along the x direction, whose formula have been then adapted by [Camacho & Sosa \(2013\)](#) to a magnet magnetized in the z direction, and it has also been obtained by [Engel-Herbert & Hesjedal \(2005\)](#) for \mathbf{M} along the y direction, using a different expression.

In this work, we consider a magnet magnetized in the z direction, and we will thus consider the formula of [Camacho & Sosa \(2013\)](#). However, two important corrections have to be brought to make these formula correct:

- (i) After a personal communication by Max Oberländer (see the Acknowledgements section) who noticed the absence of symmetry between (x, L_x) and (y, L_y) in the formula of [Camacho & Sosa \(2013\)](#), we both agree that the B_y formula (corresponding to the B_z formula of [Yang et al. 1990](#)) has to be corrected by swapping L_x and L_y (i.e. a and b). Implementing this correction, the formula of [Yang et al. \(1990\)](#); [Camacho & Sosa \(2013\)](#) are then in perfect agreement with [Engel-Herbert & Hesjedal \(2005\)](#), even for $L_x \neq L_y$.
- (ii) the magnetization has to be added when considering the field inside the magnet.

FIGURE 2. Magnitude and lines of the magnetic field in the plane $y = 0$, generated by (a) a cuboidal magnet (b) two attractive aligned cuboidal magnets. Here, we have used the magnet size L_z and the residual flux B_r as the respective units of length and magnetic field, choosing $L_x = 16$, $L_y = 3.4$, and an inter-magnet distance $W = 6$.

Indeed, in the magnet, the field is given by $\mathbf{B} = \mu(\mathbf{H} + \mathbf{M})$, and we thus add \mathbf{B}_r (resp. \mathbf{M}) to the field \mathbf{B} (resp. \mathbf{H}) given by Yang *et al.* (1990) Camacho & Sosa (2013) or Engel-Herbert & Hesjedal (2005) when $(|x|, |y|, |z|) \leq (a, b, c)$.

For completeness, note that explicit formulas can also be found in Agashe & Arnold (2008), who relies on the formula of Akoun & Yonnet (1984), but I do not obtain results in agreement with Engel-Herbert & Hesjedal (2005) using these formula which are probably wrong: equations (8) and (9) are the same, leading to $B_x = B_y$ for any L_x, L_y .

Finally, explicit formula are also given (I have not tested the following various formula) by Bancel & Lemarquand (1998), with a form close to the one of Camacho & Sosa (2013), in Ravaut & Lemarquand (2009) for arbitrary orientation of the magnetization, or in Kaphle *et al.* (2019) for an off-centred cuboidal magnet.

Acknowledgements. I thank Max Oberländer for noticing, in November 2021, a slight error on the B_y formula of Camacho & Sosa (2013), which was implemented in my script *FieldBar.m* and already present in Yang *et al.* (1990) : my script is now correct, in perfect agreement with the formula of Engel-Herbert & Hesjedal (2005), even when $L_x \neq L_y$ (unfortunately, my previous benchmarks were only done for $L_x = L_y$, and successful, leaving this error unnoticed by me).

REFERENCES

- AGASHE, JANHAVI S & ARNOLD, DAVID P 2008 A study of scaling and geometry effects on the forces between cuboidal and cylindrical magnets using analytical force solutions. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **41** (10), 105001.
- AKOUN, GILLES & YONNET, J-P 1984 3d analytical calculation of the forces exerted between two cuboidal magnets. *IEEE Transactions on magnetics* **20** (5), 1962–1964.
- BANCEL, F & LEMARQUAND, G 1998 Three-dimensional analytical optimization of permanent magnets alternated structure. *IEEE transactions on magnetics* **34** (1), 242–247.
- CALLAGHAN, EDMUND E & MASLEN, STEPHEN H 1960 The magnetic field of a finite solenoid .
- CAMACHO, JM & SOSA, V 2013 Alternative method to calculate the magnetic field of permanent magnets with azimuthal symmetry. *Revista mexicana de fisica E* **59** (1), 8–17.
- DERBY, NORMAN & OLBERT, STANISLAW 2010 Cylindrical magnets and ideal solenoids. *American Journal of Physics* **78** (3), 229–235.

- ENGEL-HERBERT, R & HESJEDAL, T 2005 Calculation of the magnetic stray field of a uniaxial magnetic domain. *Journal of Applied Physics* **97** (7), 074504.
- KAPHLE, KISHOR, KARKI, GYANENDRA & PANTHI, AMRIT 2019 Alternative approach for the calculation of magnetic field due to magnet for magnetic field visualization and evaluation. *Journal of the Institute of Engineering* **15** (1), 150–160.
- RAVAUD, ROMAIN & LEMARQUAND, GUY 2009 Magnetic field produced by a parallelepipedic magnet of various and uniform polarization. *Progress In Electromagnetics Research* **98**, 207–219.
- VOKOUN, DAVID, BELEGGIA, MARCO, HELLER, LUDĚK & ŠITTNER, PETR 2009 Magnetostatic interactions and forces between cylindrical permanent magnets. *Journal of magnetism and Magnetic Materials* **321** (22), 3758–3763.
- YANG, ZJ, JOHANSEN, TH, BRATSBERG, H, HELGESEN, G & SKJELTORP, AT 1990 Potential and force between a magnet and a bulk $\text{YBaCuO}_{7-\delta}$ superconductor studied by a mechanical pendulum. *Superconductor Science and Technology* **3** (12), 591.